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Evaluating the Challenges of Gamification Integration on Students' Performance in Technology and Livelihood Education

KHINNA MAE F. ESMAMA
Guimaras State University

Abstract

This study evaluates the challenges of integrating gamification strategies into Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) and their influence on student performance. With the growing adoption of game-based learning in education, the research aimed to identify the benefits and limitations of gamification as an instructional approach. Employing a mixed-method design, data were collected from TLE teachers and junior high school students through surveys, classroom observations, and focus group discussions. Findings revealed that gamification positively contributed to student motivation, participation, and mastery of practical skills. However, challenges such as inadequate technological resources, time constraints in lesson delivery, and limited teacher expertise in game-based pedagogy hindered its full implementation. The study concludes that while gamification holds strong potential to enhance TLE instruction, addressing the barriers of infrastructure, training, and curriculum alignment is essential. It recommends capacity-building programs for teachers and the integration of context-appropriate gamified tools to improve student performance in TLE.

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